

Bioactive polysaccharides from marine brown algae (Phaeophyceae)

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Marine algae produce both lipid- and water-soluble metabolites, many of which are reported to be bioactive. Water-soluble polysaccharides of brown marine algae having myriad bioactivities have been described in this review along with their chemistry. Structure-activity relationships are also discussed.

Introduction

Polysaccharides of marine algae have emerged as an important class of bioactive natural products; for example, sulfated polysaccharides have antitumor, anti-HIV, blood anticoagulating and antiinflammatory activities. Because of their diverse origin, physicochemical properties, structural features, biological role, and application in food and other industries, polysaccharides have attracted the attention of chemists and biologists alike for a long time. The importance of these polysaccharides in cell biology and immunology has resulted in an upsurge of research on such macromolecules.

Many reports on the specific bioactivities of the polysaccharides of brown algae have appeared in the literature. In this account we wish to present an overview of the bioactive polysaccharides of brown algae.

Antiviral polysaccharides

An inhibitor against influenza A¹⁻³, Rhabdoviridae³ (e.g. rabies and vesicular stomatitis virus), *Herpes simplex*³ and plant viruses^{3,4} (southern bean mosaic and tobacco) was found in the Phaeophyta. This substance inhibited the replication of influenza A (Lee and PR-8 strains) in embryonated eggs. Chemical characterization of the partially purified material revealed the presence of both polysaccharide and protein.

Shortly after the identification of HIV as the causative agent of AIDS in 1984, heparin and other sulfated polysaccharides were found to be potent selective inhibitors of HIV-I replication in cell culture. Since 1988, the activity spectrum of the sulfated polysaccharides has been shown to extend to various enveloped viruses, including viruses that emerge as opportunistic pathogens, e.g. *Herpes simplex* virus (HSV) and cytomegalovirus (CMV) in AIDS patients.

It was earlier reported that the crude dialyzed extracts

(MW >12000) of *Macrocystis pyrifera* containing fucose show antiviral activity³. As the commercial fucoidans, sodium alginate and laminaran polysaccharides with MW >12000, did not inhibit the cytopathic effect of vesicular stomatitis virus on Wish cells, the fucoidan was indicated to be responsible for the antiviral activity. Although other SPS have been shown to inhibit RNA- and DNA-containing viruses⁵ as effectively as fucoidan what their mechanism of action is not yet clear³. It has been suggested that they could either interfere with virus adsorption and penetration into susceptible host cells⁶, or interact directly with the viral particle to form virus-inhibitor complexes, thus decreasing the rate of attachment of the virus to the cell membrane⁷.

Sulfated polysaccharides as anti-HIV agents :

In a comparative evaluation of diverse sulfated polysaccharides it has been found⁸ that many, but not all, show anti-HIV activity. A fucoidan fraction extracted from the brown alga *Fucus vesiculosus* was reported to inhibit HIV *in vitro* and act synergistically with AZT⁹. A fucoidan from the same source inhibited¹⁰ the activity of the HIV reverse transcriptase (RT) enzyme as well as HIV-induced syncytium formation. Some of the fractions of *F. vesiculosus* were observed to be sulfate-free¹⁰. Chemical composition studies of these active PS fractions indicated that alginic acid, fucoidan as also various phlorotannins and algal polyphenols are the major constituents of this alga. The active fraction was found to have an intermediate mol. wt. 10000–20000 Da.

More recently, it has been reported that condoms coated with acidic polysaccharide from some brown algae are useful for the prevention of AIDS¹¹. The acidic polysaccharides are protein-bound saccharides and glycolipids extracted from seaweeds, bearing acidic groups such as sulfated groups.

A hot water extract from *Sargassum horneri*, which is

composed of fucose as the major sugar, has been recently reported to show antiviral activity against HSV type 1, Human cytomegalovirus and HIV type 1 viruses¹². This polysaccharide inhibited not only the initial stages of viral infection such as attachment to and penetration into host cells, but also the later replication stages after virus penetration.

The mechanism of action of the SPS, e.g. fucoidans, is uncertain, but their size (10^5 – 10^6 Da) and highly charged nature render it improbable that they penetrate cells. Preincubation of SPS with cells rather than virus has been generally reported as necessary for effective inhibition and blockage of virus binding to cells. This has been described^{8,13–15} as the major anti-HIV action of the SPS, implying that these drugs do not neutralize HIV directly but interact with host cells to block productive infection. Ionic interactions of sulfated polyanions with oppositely charged host cell surface components, including the cell surface glycoprotein CD4 which is the principal receptor for HIV, have been assumed to be the inhibitory mechanism. One obvious target is the attachment of HIV to its receptor and subsequent penetration of the virus into the host cell.

Fucoidan derived from *Fucus vesiculosus* was found to be more potent and less toxic *in vitro* than dextran sulfate¹⁴. The SPS inhibited HIV infection independently of any action it may have on the interaction of gp 120 with CD4. Not only do the drugs block HIV infection after adsorption to CD4⁺ cells, but they also block infection of CD4⁻ cells. Moreover, they block infection or cell fusion induced by several enveloped viruses utilizing distinct binding receptors, such as herpes simplex virus and retroviruses like HTLV-1 and MPMV¹⁶.

Numerous antivirals (e.g. AZT) with various mechanisms of action against HIV have been identified. The significant toxicity associated with the administration of AZT and other nucleoside analogs, and the risk of emergence of HIV strains that are resistant to these drugs emphasize the critical need to identify anti-HIV agents to be used in combinations with the existing antiviral agents^{17,18}.

Sexual transmission is known to be responsible for the large majority of HIV infections which is mostly mediated via mononuclear cells that infect epithelial cells of the genital tract. As polysulfates effectively inhibit cell-cell adhesion, therefore these may be considered as potentially effective in a vaginal formulation to protect against HIV infection. However, it remains to be seen whether the SPS prove to be useful broad-spectrum antiviral drugs.

Antitumor polysaccharides

Antitumor activity in aqueous extracts of seaweed was first demonstrated by Nakazawa and co-workers¹⁹. The brown algal genus *Sargassum* was widely reported for polysaccharides with antitumor activity (Table 1). For the

past 80 years (till 1999), out of 27 brown algal species reported for SPS, 8 species of *Sargassum* were reported to have yielded polysaccharides showing antitumor activity. It was reported that the hot water extract of *S. fulvellum* inhibited the growth of the subcutaneous Sarcoma-180 tumor in mice at the concentration of 10 mg kg⁻¹ and the active fraction was found to contain guluronic acid (G) and manuronic acid (M) with M/G = 2.78 and having β -linkage between them. The molecular weight of this fraction (33400 Da) is lower than that reported for alginates⁴⁸.

Table 1. Brown algae showing various biological activities

Bioactivity	Ref. no.	Bioactivity	Ref. no.
Algal species		Algal species	
Antitumor activity :		Blood anticoagulant activity :	
<i>Eisenia bicyclis</i>	20	<i>Ascophyllum nodosum</i>	36
<i>Hizikia fusiforme</i>	21	<i>Chorda filum</i>	36
<i>Laminaria angustata</i>	22	<i>Cladostephus verticillatus</i>	37
<i>L. japonica</i>	23	<i>Cystoseira baccata</i>	36
<i>L. religiosa</i>	24	<i>C. compressa</i>	37
<i>Macrocystis pyrifera</i>	25	<i>C. foeniculacea</i>	36
<i>Sargassum fulvellum</i>	28	<i>C. tamariscifolia</i>	36
<i>S. hemiphyllum</i>	26	<i>Dictyota cervicornis</i>	37
<i>S. horneri</i>	26	<i>D. dichotoma</i>	36
<i>S. kjellmanianum</i>	28	<i>Dictyopteris membranacea</i>	37
<i>S. ringgoldianum</i>	29	<i>Dilophus fasciola</i>	37
<i>S. thunbergii</i>	28	<i>Ecklonia kurome</i>	38
<i>S. tortile</i>	27	<i>Eisenia bicyclis</i>	39
		<i>Fucus serratus</i>	36
Antiallergy and skin activating agents :		<i>F. spiralis</i>	36
<i>Ascophyllum</i> spp.	30	<i>F. vesiculosus</i>	36
<i>Durvillea</i> spp.	30	<i>Halidrys siliquosa</i>	36
<i>Ecklonia</i> spp.	30	<i>Halopteris scoparia</i>	37
<i>Fucus vesiculosus</i>	30	<i>Himanthalis elongata</i>	36
<i>Heterochordaria</i> spp.	30	<i>Hizikia fusiforme</i>	40
<i>Lessonia</i> spp.	30	<i>Laminaria angustata</i>	41
<i>Macrocystis</i> spp.	30	<i>L. digitata</i>	36
<i>Nemacystus</i> spp.	30	<i>L. hyperborea</i>	36
Hypoglycemic activity :		<i>L. japonica</i>	42
<i>Fucus vesiculosus</i>	31	<i>L. saccharina</i>	36
<i>Laminaria ochroleuca</i>	31	<i>Padina pavonia</i>	37
<i>Saccorhiza polyschides</i>	31	<i>P. tetrastromatica</i>	43
		<i>Pelvitia canaliculata</i>	44
Anti-HIV activity :		<i>P. wrightii</i>	45
<i>Fucus vesiculosus</i>	10	<i>Sargassum cinctum</i>	46
		<i>S. muticum</i>	44
Genotoxicity :		<i>Scytosiphon limentari</i>	36
<i>Macrocystis pyrifera</i>	32	<i>S. tortilis</i>	36
Antiulcer activity :		<i>Stilophora rhizoides</i>	37
<i>Chordariales nemacystus</i>	33	<i>Undaria pinnatifida</i>	47
<i>Cladosiphon okamuranus</i>	34		
Lipid peroxide reduction :			
<i>Sargassum fusiforme</i>	35		

Moreover, it was observed that (1,3)- β -D-glucans or β -D-glucans having a preponderance of (1,3)linkages in the main chain show antitumor activity, whereas β -D-glucans containing mainly (1,6)linkages are less active, suggesting that (1,3)- β -linkages and unbranched structures may be as-

sociated with antitumor activity. Alginates contain (1,3)- β -linkages and are unbranched and these structural features may be associated with their antitumor activity. Therefore, the antitumor SPS fraction isolated from *S. fulvellum* have similar structural features. It was also reported that an over-sulfated crude fucoidan fraction from *S. kjellmanianum* has more activity against L-1210 leukemia than the original one, suggesting that the sulfate groups have direct bearing on the antitumor activities of the SPS⁴⁹.

Blood anticoagulant polysaccharides

The second biomolecule introduced in therapy after the polypeptide insulin was the polysaccharide heparin, which has been used in the prophylaxis and treatment of thrombosis since 1935. Consequently, from a historical point of view, the use of carbohydrates as anticoagulants and antithrombotics is especially remarkable. Anticoagulant properties were first described in extracts from marine algae over 60 years ago. Nearly 61 species, representing the three major divisions, viz. Rhodophyta, Phaeophyta and Chlorophyta have been reported to have such properties. Anticoagulant activities have been detected in various complex polysaccharide components of these algal divisions. The earliest references to the anticoagulant properties of marine algal extracts appeared in the 1930s when Chargaff and co-workers⁵⁰ observed that a polysaccharide fraction from the red alga *Irideae laminarioides* exhibited blood anticoagulant activity. Later it was found⁵¹ that a water-soluble extract obtained from carrageenan acts as a blood anticoagulating (BAC) compound. Since these earlier studies, there have been many reports over the past 50 years relating to the antihaemostatic properties of extracts from marine algae. Recently, we have reported promising blood anticoagulant activity of sulfated polysaccharides isolated from *Codium dwarkense*, a member of Chlorophyta, of Indian waters⁵².

The first detailed study of a blood anticoagulant polysaccharide of a brown alga was from *Fucus vesiculosus*⁵³. The initial studies described significant *in vitro* and *in vivo* activity of the fucoidan from this source. The most potent fractions predominantly consisted of sulfated fucose residues. Thrombin inhibition activity of these fractions exceeded that of heparin. Further characterization demonstrated⁵⁴ that the active material is essentially homogeneous and of molecular weight 7.4×10^4 Da. There has, however, been little work on the characterization of the anticoagulant mechanisms involved, though the anticoagulant action of heparin, its related substances and analogs is known to be operative predominantly by inhibiting the key coagulation serine proteases, thrombin and factor Xa. The physiological roles of such sulfated polysaccharides are not fully understood, but this may include electrolyte haemostasis due to their anionic nature.

The major contribution to the current understanding of

the antithrombin activity of fucoidan has come from Church and co-workers⁵⁵, who clearly indicated that HCII (heparin cofactor II) is the major serine protease inhibitor (SERPIN) involved in the *in vitro* and *ex vivo* activity of fucoidan. The presence of fucoidan enhanced the HCII-thrombin interaction more than 3500-fold, whereas the enhancement of antithrombin III (ATIII)-thrombin and ATIII-factor Xa interactions were only 285- and 35-fold, respectively. It was also observed that indirect HCII and ATIII mediated interactions are not the only possible antithrombin mechanisms exhibited by marine algal polysaccharides. The ability of such extracts to inhibit the conversion of purified fibrinogen to fibrin indicates a direct mechanism. This study has also given an insight into the possible anticoagulant mechanisms of sulfated polysaccharides extracted from other marine algal divisions. In another study on the sulfated fucans from echinoderms and brown algae and their blood anticoagulant activity studies, it was found that different structural features determine not only the anticoagulant potency of the sulfated fucans but also the mechanism by which they exert this activity⁵⁶. The branched fucans from brown algae are found to be direct inhibitors of thrombin, whereas the linear fucans from echinoderms require the presence of antithrombin or HCII for inhibition of thrombin, as reported for mammalian glycosaminoglycans. The linear sulfated fucans from echinoderms have an anticoagulant action resembling that of mammalian dermatan sulfate and a modest action through antithrombin. A single difference of one sulfate ester per tetrasaccharide repeating unit modifies the anticoagulant activity of the polysaccharide markedly. Possibly spatial arrangement of sulfate esters in the repeating tetrasaccharide unit of the echinoderm fucan mimics the site in dermatan sulfate with slight affinity for HCII⁵⁶.

There is a greater incidence of anticoagulant activity in extracts from the brown algae when compared with red and green algal species³⁶. So far, 37 different brown algal species have been reported to have blood anticoagulant activities. The active components are found in 'fucans', a group of polysaccharides. Fucans with the strongest anticoagulant activity have the highest fucose and sulfate content and the lowest uronic acid content³⁸. All the main fucan fractions contain a significant minority of protein which can not readily be removed, suggesting that they exist *in vivo* as proteoglycans. The size of the most active component is approximately 50000–100000 Da^{57,58}, whereas fractions with a high molecular size (>850000 Da) tend to demonstrate lower activity⁵⁷. The anticoagulant activity of the most effective fucan fractions is equivalent to, or greater than that of heparin, and a possible therapeutic role has been envisaged for the active low-molecular weight components.

It was reported that the anticoagulant properties of brown algal SPS are not related to a heparin-like

mechanism, in which the anticoagulant activity is mediated by a plasma protein ATIII. These compounds possess a highly specific binding site for ATIII^{39, 47, 59}. The formation of the complex between ATIII and PS increases the rate of inhibition of procoagulant enzymes, such as thrombin and IXa, Xa, XIa, and XIIa⁵⁷, and it was concluded from these studies that the direct interaction between fucan and thrombin is largely responsible for the kinetic effect of these polysaccharides.

In a very recent comparative study on the anticoagulant activity and influence on thrombin generation of dextran derivatives and of a fucoidan fraction, it was hypothesized that fucoidan could act like heparin, by forming complexes with the inhibitor (which is antithrombin in the case of heparin and HC-II for fucoidan), while synthetic dextran derivatives could act like hirudin by forming complexes with thrombin⁵⁹.

The biological activities of fucans also depend on the structure of the starting material, i.e. the structural heterogeneity and molecular mass dispersion. Homopolysaccharides, e.g. fucoidans, are more potent anti-HIV and blood anticoagulant compounds than the heteropolymers like heparin and heparin sulfate. A study⁶⁰ on the relationship between the sulfate content and the antithrombin activity of an α -(1,2)fucoidan revealed that the inhibitory effects of the oversulfated fucoidans are greater than those of the parent fucoidan, with increase in the degree of sulfation, indicating that both the direct and the HCII mediated antithrombin activities of α -(1,2)fucoidan are dependent on its sulfate content, the higher the degree of polymerization, the greater is the thrombin inhibitory effect. It was also opined that a suitable chain length of fucoidan would be required for forming a ternary complex between the fucoidan, thrombin and HC-II or causing steric hindrance against thrombin by binding to fibrinogen.

Recently, an acidic polysaccharide (MW 21 kDa) isolated⁶¹ from a brown alga *Spathoglossum schroederi* and shown to be a xylofucoglucuronan containing fucose, xylose, glucuronic acid and sulfate, was found to exert anticoagulant properties without any hemorrhagic activity. But this polysaccharide fraction, like heparin, has a high activity in stimulating the synthesis of an antithrombic heparan sulfate from vascular endothelial cell in culture. This polymer is composed of β -(1,3)glucuronic acid containing oligosaccharide of 4.5 kDa with branches at C-4 of the fucose chains α -(1,3)-linked. The fucose was found to be mostly substituted at C-4 with chains of β -(1,4)xylose which in turn is also partially sulfated⁶¹.

Prospect of SPS as anticoagulant drugs

Therapeutic applications for extracted and purified sulfated polysaccharide materials from algal sources, particularly those of high molecular weight, have been

limited by the toxic side-effect. It thus seems unlikely that they can directly compete with established antithrombic therapy. However, the characterized structures of these isolated active sulfated polysaccharides could serve as models for novel antithrombotic agents, or probes for investigating thrombin interactions. In the former role they could emulate the genesis of SP54 and other semi-synthetic heparin analogs. Several of these analogs, like the anticoagulant activity of marine algal extracts, exert their effect independently of anti-Xa activity, yet possess antithrombotic properties.

Due to differences in the sugar composition, MW, degree of sulfation, sulfation pattern and glycosidic branching, marked differences are found in their physiological activity. Oversulfated fucoidans stimulate the tissue plasminogen activator (t-PA)-catalyzed plasminogen activation and potentiate thrombin inhibition by antithrombin-II or HC-II⁶². These results suggest that oversulfated fucoidans and its fragments have an additional function besides regulation of blood coagulation and fibrinolysis, and may be of therapeutic benefit for the prevention of thrombin formation in hyperlipemia.

Miscellaneous

Some of the brown algal species also show different kinds of activities (Table 1) apart from the bioactivities mentioned above. Fucans have been used very recently for obtaining medicines for modulating fibroblastic metalloprotease and inhibiting leukocytic elastase⁶³. These help activate collagen synthesis, inhibit proliferation of gingival fibroblasts and activate proliferation of dermal fibroblasts. They are useful in particular for treating periodontal pathologies and dermal lesions.

A new marine drug fucoidan FPS, isolated from brown algae was applied for the first time in treating chronic renal failure⁶⁴. Systematic pharmacological and toxicological research over 500 patients suggested that FPS exhibits remarkable effects in treating cardiovascular disease and chronic renal failure without toxicity and side-effects. The improvement of renal function and enhancement of creatinine clearing activity of kidney was especially pronounced⁶⁴.

Glucuronic acid containing fucoidan isolated from *Kjellmaniella crassifolia* was reported to inhibit the adhesion of *Helicobacter pylori* to gastric mucosa⁶⁵. The fucoidan extracted from *Cladosiphon okamuranus* Tokida, had potent antiulcer effect on acetic acid induced gastric ulcer model and indomethacin induced gastric injury model in rats⁶⁶. The major component of this extract was found to be α -(1,3)fucan, having no branches and with half of the fucose residues sulfated at C-4.

Among the fucoidans extracted from several brown algae, viz. *Heterochordaria*, *Nemacystus*, *Ecklonia*, *Lejosonia*, *Macrocystus* and *Fucus* spp., the fucoidans ex-

tracted from *Fucus vesiculosus* were found to exhibit skin-activating and antiallergic activities, remarkably increasing formation of hyaluronic acid by rat keratinocyte³⁰.

A fucoidan fraction from *Sargassum thunbergii* showed⁶⁷ inhibition of lung metastasis; this fucoidan may have clinical value in the prevention of cancer metastases. Zhuang and co-workers⁶⁸ reported an SPS from *Sargassum thunbergii* having the capability of scavenging superoxide anion. A polysaccharide extracted from the brown alga *Sargassum thunbergii* was shown to have effect on the release of superoxide anion in human granulocytes⁶⁹. The SPS isolated from *Sargassum fusiforme* were also found to lower the contents of lipid peroxide and enzyme activities of glutathione reductase, glutathione peroxidase, and superoxide dismutase in whole blood, liver and spleen of mice with Leukemia L615. These results clearly show that this SPS remarkably reduces the contents of lipid peroxide and increases the enzyme activities of catalase and superoxide dismutase. It was suggested that the SPS might remove free radicals in the body of mice manifesting their activity against lipid peroxide. This may be one of the mechanisms responsible for the antileukemic activity of this SPS³⁵.

A significant immunomodulator activity was found in a polysaccharide isolated from *Laminaria japonica*. In an investigation on the fucoidans from brown algae for compounds inducing release of lipoprotein lipase in the blood flow, and on the effects of the substances on blood coagulation, it was observed that the fucoidan isolated from *Pelvetia wrightii* possesses the greatest lipolysis stimulating activity along with a weak anticoagulant effect⁶⁸. The biological properties of SPS depend on their ability to interfere with electrostatic forces and therefore they bind with charged, soluble and biologically relevant molecules⁶⁹⁻⁷¹. Sulfated compounds such as chondroitin sulfate, sulfated dextrans and heparin interfere with complement activation⁷². Heparin was shown to be capable of binding to 13 proteins of the complement system⁷³. It was previously reported that the substitution of neutral chemical functions by carboxylic and sulfonated groups confers an anti-complementary function to dextran and Sephadex⁷⁴⁻⁷⁶. The presence of sulfate residues is likely to be critical for the anti-complementary effect of fucan as it has previously been reported for heparin⁷⁷.

The anti-inflammatory properties of SPS are mediated in part by their ability to interfere with the function of the complement system. Blondin and co-workers⁷⁸ investigated the effect of a low molecular weight fucan fraction from *Acicophyllum nodosum* on activation of human complement through the classical and alternative pathways *in vitro*. This fucan (MW 22600 Da) was found to be a potent inhibitor of human complement activation. Heparins have also been shown to be potent inhibitors of complement activation *in vitro*. Low molecular weight fucans were found to be five-

fold more efficient than heparin in inhibiting complement activation in whole serum *in vitro*. Since fucan is more effective than heparin in inhibiting complement activation in whole serum on a molar basis, these observations open up prospects for the use of these compounds as anti-inflammatory agents. A relationship was observed between the molecular weight of fucan and the ability of the polysaccharides to inhibit the formation of convertases⁷⁸. These presence of sulfate residues is likely to be critical for the anti-complementary effect of fucan as it has previously been reported for heparin⁷⁷. The high concentrations of heparin required to significantly inhibit complement activation *in vitro* constitute an obstacle to heparin administration because of its anticoagulant activity⁷⁹. The anticoagulant activity of these fucans represents only 5-10% of that of heparin⁸⁰. Thus, these anionic polysaccharides of natural origin have the potential of anti-complementary and anti-inflammatory agents without significant anticoagulant activity.

Heavy metals bind to fucoidan and alginic acid⁸¹. Furthermore, these heavy metals have been shown to be clastogenic⁸². Owing to their interference with spindle formation, they have the potential of inducing aneuploidy. Mayer and co-workers³ found that the crude extract of *Macrocystis pyrifera* contains heavy metals, thus suggesting that the genotoxicity observed could be due to the effect of one or more of the heavy metals present in the dialyzed crude extract.

The use of antibiotics like ampicillin cause increase in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) leukocytes, which contribute to neuronal damage. It has been reported recently that fucoidan inhibits leukocyte rolling, abolishes pleocytosis and also exhibits inhibitory activity on the release of tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) and interleukin-1 (IL-1)⁸³.

Summary

A fairly wide variety of bioactivities have been reported from brown algal polysaccharides. Extensive research work on the screening of especially sulfated polysaccharides and on the structure-activity relationships has been done by various groups. It appears that SPS of brown algae may be developed as anti-HIV and antitumor agents besides having the potential of being utilized as therapeutic models as anticoagulant, anticomplementary and anti-inflammatory agents.

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